

Corotational stiffness matrices for 3D truss elements

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Abstract: In this work, the tangent stiffness matrix for the geometrically nonlinear analysis of a three-dimensional truss element subjected to large displacements and rotations, and potentially large deformations, is derived based on the Corotational formulation. The tangent matrix is deduced following two equivalent approaches: variational and energy-based. The resulting tangent stiffness matrix of the element makes up the global stiffness matrix of the structure, which is used in incremental and/or iterative numerical methods to capture the geometric nonlinear response.

Keywords: Structural analysis; Geometric nonlinearity; Corotational; Truss model; Bar element;

1. Introduction

A 3D truss element is a 2-noded space bar with three degrees-of-freedom per node: translations in the directions of orthogonal axes X, Y and Z, which may be referred to global or local coordinate system. The only type of internal force in a truss element is the axial force, produced by normal stresses in the element cross-sections. There is no bending and the element is always straight.

The Corotational formulation establishes a tangent relation between nodal displacements and forces (i.e. a relation between the variation of these quantities or, equivalently, the derivative of internal forces with respect to displacements) by separating rigid-body motions from strain-producing motions. The rigid-body motions are the element translation and rotation, which do not generate internal forces and are measured with respect to the initial configuration using the global coordinate system. The only strain-producing motion of a truss element is its elongation, which generates an internal axial force and is measured with respect to a corotated configuration that translates and rotates with the element so that it eliminates all rigid-body motions. The corotated configuration defines the so-called natural system, which is not exactly a coordinate system, but the set of local displacement and force components that are related to element deformations, called natural displacements and forces (only one component in the case of a truss element).

An important characteristic of the Corotational formulation is that the natural displacements may be considered very small and, therefore, the element can be formulated as linear (infinitesimal strains) in the natural system, with the geometric nonlinearity being introduced in the transformation between the reference systems (natural and global systems). Such characteristic allows the formulation to cope very well with analyses of arbitrarily large rigid motions, but small deformations. However, a truss element may be subjected to a large axial deformation and it requires that nonlinear strain measurements be used. This consideration is left for the last section.

This work is based on the theory presented in [1–7], which has been extensively used in programs developed by the author's research group [8–19].

2. Reference Systems

The displacement and force components of the element may be referred to two systems: the global system of coordinates or the natural system of deformations.

Figure 1.a shows a truss element in the space defined by global axes XYZ . In the initial configuration, the length of the element is L_0 and the nodal coordinates are (x_1, y_1, z_1) for the first node and (x_2, y_2, z_2) for the second node. As the structure is loaded, the element moves from its original configuration to a deformed configuration, in which it assumes a length L and angles $\beta_x, \beta_y, \beta_z$ with global axes. This movement is defined by node displacements in the global axes directions, which are grouped in vector $\{d_g\}$ of Eq. (1). These displacements are responsible for a translation, a rotation, and an elongation u_n of the element. The first two are rigid-body motions that do not produce strains and stresses in the element. The elongation, given by the difference of lengths shown in Eq. (2), is the movement component that generates internal forces (in this case, axial force), being the only displacement component of the natural system of the truss element.

Figure 1.b shows the positive directions of the resulting nodal forces in the global system, which are grouped in vector $\{f_g\}$ of Eq. (3), and the only force component of the natural system: the axial force P that corresponds to the element elongation. The figure shows the positive direction of the natural internal force, which is a tensile force.

Figure 1 – Components in the global and natural systems of (a) displacements and (b) forces.

$$\{d_g\} = \{d_{x1} \quad d_{y1} \quad d_{z1} \quad d_{x2} \quad d_{y2} \quad d_{z2}\}^T \quad (1)$$

$$u_n = L - L_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\{f_g\} = \{f_{x1} \quad f_{y1} \quad f_{z1} \quad f_{x2} \quad f_{y2} \quad f_{z2}\}^T \quad (3)$$

3. Variational Approach

Using the displacements and forces in both reference systems, the tangent stiffness matrix of the element will be derived. The tangent matrix relates nodal displacements and forces in global system. In fact, due to the nonlinearity, the tangent matrix relates displacement increments to force increments, hence the term “tangent”. In other words, it involves the variation of these quantities. The relation between the variations of global displacements and global forces is obtained from the relation between the variations of other global and natural quantities, as indicated in Fig. 2. The next sections will develop the variational relations of the constitutive law (1), kinematic (2), and equilibrium (3) between the reference systems for obtaining the tangent stiffness matrix in the global system (indicated by $[K_t]$ in Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Relations between variations of global and natural quantities.

3.1 Displacements and Forces in Natural System (Constitutive Relation)

It was commented that the natural displacements might be considered very small, so engineering (infinitesimal) strains can be used in the natural system (it is also known that engineering strains are problematic in the presence of rigid-body rotation, which is not the case of the natural system). Assuming, also, linear-elastic material behavior and considering the cross-section area to be constant (typical consideration for small strain problems), the axial force is related to the element elongation as follows, where E is the elasticity modulus of the material and A is the element cross-sections area:

$$P = \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \quad (4)$$

Since only geometric nonlinearity is considered (physical linearity is preserved), the variations of these quantities are similarly related:

$$\delta P = \frac{EA}{L_0} \delta u_n \quad (5)$$

3.2 Displacements in Natural and Global Systems (Kinematic Relation)

To find a relation between displacements in natural and global systems, consider a small movement (variation) from the deformed configuration, as shown in Fig. 3. In that figure δd is the vector of net variations (difference of global displacements variations of second and first node), whose components in global system are given in Eq. (6). In the deformed configuration, the unit vector in the element axial direction is e_1 , whose components in global system are also given in Eq. (6). In the configuration after variation, the angles with global axes are $\beta'_x, \beta'_y, \beta'_z$.

Figure 3 – Small movement (variation) from the deformed configuration.

$$\{\delta d\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x2} - \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y2} - \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta d_{z2} - \delta d_{z1} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \{e_1\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos \beta_x \\ \cos \beta_y \\ \cos \beta_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

For an infinitesimal angle change, the variation of element elongation is obtained by the scalar product between the unit axial vector of deformed configuration and the net variations vector, as in Eq. (7), which gives the component of δd projected along the direction of e_1 (in other words, since $\delta L_0 = 0$ then $\delta u_n = \delta L - \delta L_0 = \delta L$).

$$\delta u_n = \{e_1\}^T \{\delta d\} \quad (7)$$

By multiplying these vectors and organizing the terms, the variation of element elongation can be related to the variation of nodal displacements in global system as shown in Eq. (8), where vector $\{r\}$ is defined.

$$\delta u_n = \left\{ -\cos \beta_x \quad -\cos \beta_y \quad -\cos \beta_z \quad \cos \beta_x \quad \cos \beta_y \quad \cos \beta_z \right\} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta d_{z1} \\ \delta d_{x2} \\ \delta d_{y2} \\ \delta d_{z2} \end{Bmatrix} = \{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\} \quad (8)$$

Additionally, it is also necessary to determine the variation of vector $\{r\}$, as it will be required in the next sections.

$$\{\delta r\} = \{-\delta \cos \beta_x \quad -\delta \cos \beta_y \quad -\delta \cos \beta_z \quad \delta \cos \beta_x \quad \delta \cos \beta_y \quad \delta \cos \beta_z\}^T \quad (9)$$

To obtain the variation of the direction cosines, it will be considered that the element length is the same in both configurations (before and after variation). Therefore, the direction cosines of both configurations are expressed in terms of initial coordinates and nodal displacements as:

$$\cos \beta_x = \frac{(x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1)}{L} \quad \cos \beta'_x = \frac{(x_2 + dx_2 + \delta dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1 + \delta dx_1)}{L} \quad (10)$$

$$\cos \beta_y = \frac{(y_2 + dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1)}{L} \quad \cos \beta'_y = \frac{(y_2 + dy_2 + \delta dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1 + \delta dy_1)}{L} \quad (11)$$

$$\cos \beta_z = \frac{(z_2 + dz_2) - (z_1 + dz_1)}{L} \quad \cos \beta'_z = \frac{(z_2 + dz_2 + \delta dz_2) - (z_1 + dz_1 + \delta dz_1)}{L} \quad (12)$$

During the small change of element position, the variation of a direction cosine is obtained from the difference of its value in both configurations, which results in:

$$\delta \cos \beta_x = \cos \beta'_x - \cos \beta_x = \frac{\delta dx_2 - \delta dx_1}{L} \quad (13)$$

$$\delta \cos \beta_y = \cos \beta'_y - \cos \beta_y = \frac{\delta dy_2 - \delta dy_1}{L} \quad (14)$$

$$\delta \cos \beta_z = \cos \beta'_z - \cos \beta_z = \frac{\delta dz_2 - \delta dz_1}{L} \quad (15)$$

Using these results in Eq. (9), we arrive at the following relation between the variation of vector $\{r\}$ and global displacements, where matrix $[z]$ is defined to write it in a compact form in Eq. (17):

$$\{\delta r\} = \frac{1}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta d_{x1} \\ \delta d_{y1} \\ \delta d_{z1} \\ \delta d_{x2} \\ \delta d_{y2} \\ \delta d_{z2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$$\{\delta r\} = \frac{1}{L} [z] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (17)$$

3.3 Forces in Natural and Global Systems (Equilibrium Relation)

Figure 4 shows the positive directions of the components of nodal forces in the local system of the element (identified by apostrophes, to differentiate from the components of the global system), and the force component of the natural system (the axial force P). It is easy to establish a relation between the forces of these two systems, which is given by Eq. (18) and written in compact form in Eq. (19), where vector $\{S\}$ is identified.

Figure 4 – Force components in natural and local systems.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f'_{x1} \\ f'_{y1} \\ f'_{z1} \\ f'_{x2} \\ f'_{y2} \\ f'_{z2} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} P \quad (18)$$

$$\{f_l\} = \{S\} P \quad (19)$$

Using the well-known rotation transformation matrix of coordinate systems, $[R]$, the nodal forces in local system are related to nodal forces in global system as follows, where c_{ij} is the cosine of the angle between element local axis i and global axis j :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f_{x1} \\ f_{y1} \\ f_{z1} \\ f_{x2} \\ f_{y2} \\ f_{z2} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{xx} & c_{yx} & c_{zx} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_{xy} & c_{yy} & c_{zy} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_{xz} & c_{yz} & c_{zz} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{xx} & c_{yx} & c_{zx} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{xy} & c_{yy} & c_{zy} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{xz} & c_{yz} & c_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f'_{x1} \\ f'_{y1} \\ f'_{z1} \\ f'_{x2} \\ f'_{y2} \\ f'_{z2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\{f_g\} = [R]\{f_l\} \quad (21)$$

Using Equations (19) and (21), we can now determine the relation between force components in global and natural systems as follows. Note that the product of rotation matrix $[R]$ by vector $\{S\}$, that relates forces of local and natural systems, results in the same vector $\{r\}$, defined in Eq. (8), that relates the variations of element elongation and global displacements (see the reason in Appendix A):

$$\{f_g\} = [R]\{S\}P \quad (22)$$

$$\{f_g\} = \{r\}P \quad (23)$$

Once the relation between global and natural forces is known, the variation of these quantities, in which we are interested, is obtained by the product rule:

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \{r\}\delta P + \{\delta r\}P \quad (24)$$

3.4 Tangent Stiffness Matrix

All the necessary relations between global and natural quantities have been established in the previous sections in order to develop a variationally consistent tangent stiffness matrix in the global system. These relations are illustrated in Fig. 5, where the bold equation indicates the unknown relation that is being sought. This unknown relation is provided by the tangent matrix, which is also defined as the differentiation of internal global forces with respect to global displacements (tangent to the curve of nodal displacements versus nodal forces).

Figure 5 – Established relations between the variations of global and natural quantities.

Equation (24), at the bottom of Fig. 5, is written as Eq. (25) by using Eq. (17) to express the variation of vector $\{r\}$. Equation (5), on the right side of Fig. 5, is then applied to express the variation of natural force in terms of the variation of natural displacement, resulting in Eq. (26). Finally, Eq. (8), at the top of Fig. 5, is used to replace the variation of natural displacement in terms of the variation of global displacements, resulting in Eq. (27).

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \{r\} \delta P + \frac{P}{L} [z] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (25)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \{r\} \frac{EA}{L_0} \delta u_n + \frac{P}{L} [z] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (26)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \frac{EA}{L_0} \{r\} \{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\} + \frac{P}{L} [z] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (27)$$

Observing that $\{\delta d_g\}$ is a common factor on the right hand side of Eq. (27), the relation between variations of global forces and global displacements is finally achieved in Eq. (28). This expression provides the tangent stiffness matrix of a 3D truss element referred to the global system. It can be observed that the tangent matrix is generated by the sum of two stiffness components: an elastic stiffness matrix $[K_e]$, which depends only on element properties, and a geometric stiffness matrix $[K_g]$, which depends on the internal axial force.

$$\{\delta f_g\} = \left(\frac{EA}{L_0} \{r\} \{r\}^T + \frac{P}{L} [z] \right) \{\delta d_g\} \quad (28)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = ([K_e] + [K_g]) \{\delta d_g\} \quad (29)$$

$$\{\delta f_g\} = [K_t] \{\delta d_g\} \quad (30)$$

If we expand the expression of the elastic matrix in the global system, we obtain the result below, where c_{ij} stand for $\cos(\beta_i) * \cos(\beta_j)$:

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \{r\} \{r\}^T = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} c_{xx} & c_{xy} & c_{xz} & -c_{xx} & -c_{xy} & -c_{xz} \\ & c_{yy} & c_{yz} & -c_{yx} & -c_{yy} & -c_{yz} \\ & & c_{zz} & -c_{zx} & -c_{zy} & -c_{zz} \\ & & & c_{xx} & c_{xy} & c_{xz} \\ \text{sym} & & & & c_{yy} & c_{yz} \\ & & & & & c_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

Considering an element with its local axes aligned with global axes (i.e. assuming $\beta_x = 0$ and $\beta_y = \beta_z = 90^\circ$), we can check the result for the elastic matrix referred to the local system of the element:

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

The geometric stiffness matrix, on the other hand, is invariant with respect to rotations (i.e. $[K_g] = [R]^T[K_g][R]$) and is, therefore, identical in the local and global coordinate systems:

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L}[z] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

Note that the geometric matrix has stiffness coefficients in the axial positions that contribute with the gain or loss of stiffness during elongation. Because of that, this matrix should be used in the Corotational formulation only when large strains are considered to compute the internal axial force. Otherwise, the axial stiffness coefficients will be useless to converge to an equilibrium solution that is based on small strains. This is because the solution of a purely axial nonlinear analysis that uses engineering strains is the same of a linear analysis, so the change in axial stiffness, promoted by the axial coefficients of the geometric matrix, will slow down the convergence process (see the related material on 2D truss elements).

The axial coefficients emerge as a result of considering a constant element length when computing the variation of vector $\{r\}$ in Eq. (9). If this consideration was not made (a more complex task in 3D), we would obtain the geometric matrix of Eq. (34), which is given in the local coordinate system (differently from the previous, this one is not invariant to rotations). This matrix accounts only for the change of internal force directions during rigid-body rotation, which is the main effect captured by the geometric stiffness.

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

It is interesting to observe that it would not be possible to derive the geometric stiffness matrix directly in the local system, because it comes from the variation of vector $\{r\}$ – the second term of Eq. (24) – and it only exists because this vector is a function of the rotation angle, so the product rule is applied to obtain Eq. (24) from Eq. (23). The reason for this is that the local and natural systems are aligned, so a transformation between these systems would not cause the internal forces to change direction.

4. Energy-Based Approach

The tangent stiffness matrix of the 3D truss element could be derived by directly applying constitutive, kinematic and equilibrium relations between the two reference systems because of the simplicity of this element. A more general approach for dealing with complex finite elements is based on energy principles. For the truss element studied here, the potential energy is:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} P u_n \quad (35)$$

4.1 Internal Forces Vector

The first derivative of the potential energy with respect to the vector of global nodal displacements gives us the internal force vector in the global system:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (36)$$

Using the product rule to derive the potential energy, we obtain:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{1}{2} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + u_n \frac{\partial P}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) \quad (37)$$

As explained in section 3.1, engineering strain is used to relate the axial force with the element elongation according to Eq. (4), which leads us to rewrite the previous expression as follows:

$$\{f_g\} = \frac{1}{2} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + u_n \frac{EA}{L_0} \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} + P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) = P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (38)$$

It is necessary to calculate the derivatives of the natural displacement (element elongation) with respect to each component of global displacements. To do so, we express the elongation as the difference of deformed and initial lengths and note that the derivatives of the initial length with respect to global displacements are null, leaving only the deformed length, which is written in terms of initial node coordinates and global displacements in Eq. (40).

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial (L - L_0)}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \{d_g\}} \quad (39)$$

$$L = \sqrt{\left((x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1) \right)^2 + \left((y_2 + dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1) \right)^2 + \left((z_2 + dz_2) - (z_1 + dz_1) \right)^2} \quad (40)$$

Therefore, the derivative of element elongation with respect to the vector of global displacements is given in Eq. (41), and the vector of internal nodal forces in global system is given in Eq. (42), which is the same result previously obtained in Eq. (23).

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \left\{ \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x1}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{y1}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{z1}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x2}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{y2}} \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{z2}} \right\}^T = \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta_x \\ -\cos \beta_y \\ -\cos \beta_z \\ \cos \beta_x \\ \cos \beta_y \\ \cos \beta_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

$$\{f_g\} = P \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta_x \\ -\cos \beta_y \\ -\cos \beta_z \\ \cos \beta_x \\ \cos \beta_y \\ \cos \beta_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

4.2 Tangent Stiffness Matrix

The tangent stiffness is found by taking the second derivative of the potential energy with respect to the global displacements vector:

$$[K_t] = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (43)$$

This is the same of taking the first derivative of the vector of internal forces with respect to the global displacements vector. Writing the vector of internal forces as in Eq. (38), we get:

$$[K_t] = \frac{\partial \{f_g\}}{\partial \{d_g\}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \{d_g\}} \left(P \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \{d_g\}} \left(\frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right) \quad (44)$$

Using the product rule results in the expression of the tangent stiffness matrix of the truss element, which is composed of the elastic stiffness and the geometric stiffness:

$$[K_t] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T + \frac{EA}{L_0} u_n \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \right] \quad (45)$$

The elastic stiffness matrix is obtained from the first term of Eq. (45), the one that depend on the first derivatives of element elongation with respect to the vector of global displacements. Using the derivative results, given in Eq. (41), we arrive at the elastic stiffness matrix in global system, the same of Eq. (31), where cij stand for $\cos(\beta_i) * \cos(\beta_j)$:

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}} \right\}^T \quad (46)$$

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{Bmatrix} -\cos \beta_x \\ -\cos \beta_y \\ -\cos \beta_z \\ \cos \beta_x \\ \cos \beta_y \\ \cos \beta_z \end{Bmatrix} \left\{ -\cos \beta_x \quad -\cos \beta_y \quad -\cos \beta_z \quad \cos \beta_x \quad \cos \beta_y \quad \cos \beta_z \right\} \quad (47)$$

$$[K_e] = \frac{EA}{L_0} \begin{bmatrix} cxx & cxy & cxz & -cxx & -cxy & -cxz \\ & cyy & cyz & -cyx & -cyy & -cyz \\ & & czz & -czx & -czy & -czz \\ & & & cxx & cxy & cxz \\ \text{sym} & & & & cyy & cyz \\ & & & & & czz \end{bmatrix} \quad (48)$$

The geometric stiffness matrix is obtained from the second term of Eq. (45). To evaluate that term, it is necessary to determine the second derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacements vector.

$$[K_g] = P \frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} \quad (49)$$

From Eq. (39), we recall that taking the derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacements vector is the same as taking the derivative of the deformed length:

$$\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \{d_g\}^2} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y1}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{z1}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x1} \partial d_{z2}} \\ & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{z1}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y1} \partial d_{z2}} \\ & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{z1}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{z1} \partial d_{x2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{z1} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{z1} \partial d_{z2}} \\ & & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2} \partial d_{y2}} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{x2} \partial d_{z2}} \\ & \text{sym} & & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y2}^2} & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{y2} \partial d_{z2}} \\ & & & & & \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial d_{z2}^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (50)$$

Based on the expression of the deformed length of Eq. (40), it is possible to compute the second derivatives of the element elongation with respect to global displacements to get the geometric matrix in the global coordinate system (not shown). When considering an element aligned with the

global axes (i.e. assuming $\beta_x = 0$ and $\beta_y = \beta_z = 90^\circ$), the resulting geometric stiffness matrix is the same of that in Eq. (34):

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (51)$$

As explained in section 3.4, if we consider a constant element length when computing the second derivatives of element elongation, the resulting geometric matrix has stiffness coefficients in the axial positions, which make it suitable for analyses with large deformations. For example, considering the element length given in Eq. (40), the first derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacement d_{x1} is:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x1}} = - \frac{(x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1)}{\sqrt{((x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1))^2 + ((y_2 + dy_2) - (y_1 + dy_1))^2 + ((z_2 + dz_2) - (z_1 + dz_1))^2}} \quad (52)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_n}{\partial d_{x1}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial d_{x1}} = - \frac{(x_2 + dx_2) - (x_1 + dx_1)}{L} \quad (53)$$

If the denominator of Eq. (53) is considered a constant, the second derivative of the element elongation with respect to the global displacement component is:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u_n}{\partial d_{x1}^2} = \frac{1}{L} \quad (54)$$

By performing all other derivatives of Eq. (50) in the same way, we get the following geometric stiffness matrix, the same of Eq. (33):

$$[K_g] = \frac{P}{L} [z] = \frac{P}{L} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (55)$$

Appendix A – The Principle of Contragradiency

The vector whose transpose relates the variation of displacements in global and natural systems, in Eq. (8), is the same vector that relates forces in global and natural systems, in Eq. (23). This corresponds to the Principle of Contragradiency of structural analysis.

Therefore, the relation of Eq. (23) could also be derived from the Principle of Virtual Displacements, considering that the work performed by forces going through virtual displacements in the global and natural systems is equal. This is seen in Eq. (A1), where the virtual work must hold for an arbitrary virtual displacement. Writing the natural displacement in terms of global displacements, in Eq. (A2), and canceling it from the both sides of Eq. (A2), we obtain in Eq. (A3) the same relation of Eq. (23).

$$\{\delta d_g\}^T \{f_g\} = \delta u_n \cdot P \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\{\delta d_g\}^T \{f_g\} = \left(\{r\}^T \{\delta d_g\}\right)^T P \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$\{f_g\} = \{r\} P \quad (\text{A3})$$

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